

A CONCEPTUAL DESIGN FOR IMPROVING AIRCRAFT TAKE-OFF EFFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

In this article, a special model for the airplane wing is proposed. The main aim of the model is to maximize take-off efficiency of airplanes and increase the effectiveness of in-flight maneuvers. The sudden movement of a leading-edge downward-movable control surface in the main wing could, if engineered cautiously and effectively, increase the lift force of an aircraft. This could work independently of the elevator. Finally, the pros and cons of the model is discussed from different perspectives.

INTRODUCTION

“Once you have tasted flight, you will forever walk the earth with your eyes turned skyward, for there you have been, and there you will always long to return.” Leonardo da Vinci’s famous quote sums up humankind’s struggle to fly in the sky – from time immemorial. Today, that is no more a dream. The Wright brothers’ first flight could be done within the fuselage of modern airliners like the Airbus A380. Some would say flying has lost its charm. But every time you are in your seat – gripping your armrest as the plane rolls forward on the runway with flaps extended – you know that it hasn’t.

All this aside, the airline industry is a complex one – where boom-and-bust cycles are inevitable and can bring down companies from their pinnacles to a state of bankruptcy. A single crash can give rise to a long-standing saga, a single innovation can bring breakthroughs. On the whole, it is a much safer means of transportation, and undoubtedly the most convenient one.

Basics of flight

An airplane is not just a complex machine with millions of parts; it is also one of the most sensitive machines out there, with a lot of moving surfaces – a slight change in which can create a drastic outcome. An airplane flies by manipulating, with the help of movable control surfaces, the flow of air around it. The wing is designed such that the air above the wing would flow faster than the air below, and thus create a region of low air pressure above the wings – thus generating a lift force upward.

Four forces act on an airplane. The weight of the plane tends to bring it down. This is balanced by the lift force generated by the wings. The thrust of the engines tends to push the plane forward. This is balanced by air resistance, or drag.

Thus, all we need to do is generate more lift than weight and more thrust than drag, if we are to remain airborne and move forward. Thrust is easy to understand. The engines spin to create a region of low pressure just before them. This causes air to rush in, which is then passed through a compressor and ignited with the fuel in the combustion chamber. (Interestingly, part of this compressed air is circulated in the cabin, since air at high altitudes lack oxygen.) This air is then passed through the turbine station, causing the first-stage fan to spin faster and suck in more air. This incoming air will push the ignited air out from the exhaust. This backward push provides the forward thrust as a reaction force, which pushes the huge aircraft at a speed of around 170 knots on the runway. (1 knot is about 0.5 metres per second.)

What about the lift? We have the wings to generate them. Anyone who has travelled by air is aware of the huge surface area of the main wing. The wings are specially shaped to maximize lift force.

The airfoil shape of the wing manipulates the air that is flowing on top of it so that it speeds up, and the air below the wings is relatively slower. It is often said that this creates a difference in air pressure above and below the wing – with a greater pressure below. This is responsible for generating the force that pushes the wing upward. To be fair, this explanation is not fully accurate. Let us try to understand this more rigorously.

Air is a fluid. When a fluid is in motion, it must move in such a way that mass is conserved. Mass conservation places restrictions on the velocity field. Consider the steady flow of fluid through a duct (i.e., the inlet and outlet flows don't vary with time). The inflow and outflow are one-dimensional, so that the velocity v and density ρ are constant over the area A .

Applying the principle of mass conservation, since there is no flow through the side walls of the duct, the mass that comes in over area A_1 (area of inlet portion) goes out of A_2 (area of outlet portion). The flow is steady so that mass is not accumulated. Over a short time-interval Δt ,

$$\text{Volume of inflow, } V_1 = A_1 v_1 \Delta t$$

where v_1 is the velocity of the fluid when it is flowing through A_1 . Velocity times time gives distance (here, in the horizontal direction); which, when multiplied with the two-dimensional area of cross-section, gives the volume.

Similarly,

$$\text{Volume of outflow, } V_2 = A_2 v_2 \Delta t$$

where v_2 is the velocity of the fluid when it is flowing through A_2 .

$$\text{We know that } \rho \text{ (density)} = \frac{m \text{ (mass)}}{V \text{ (Volume)}}$$

$$\text{Mass in} = \rho A_1 v_1 \Delta t.$$

$$\text{Mass out} = \rho A_2 v_2 \Delta t.$$

By the law of conservation of mass,

$$\rho A_1 v_1 \Delta t = \rho A_2 v_2 \Delta t.$$

$$A_1 v_1 = A_2 v_2.$$

This is the continuity equation for steady one-dimensional flow. The equation shows that the greater the area, the lower the velocity and vice-versa. This is precisely why water from a pipe rushes out at a greater velocity if the mouth of the pipe is pinched, thus decreasing the area of cross-section. This same principle is used by airplanes too. However, it should be noted that contrary to what is often stated, velocity difference does not give rise to pressure difference, rather the opposite. Actually, the curvature of the wing is responsible for generating lift force. The key is to realize that if a streamline is curved, there must be a pressure gradient across the streamline.

The special curved shape of the wing (the airfoil) forces the air flowing over it to bend and closely follow the curved surface. When streamlines curve, they get crowded closer together above the wing. This crowding of streamlines means the pressure must drop there, while the pressure stays higher below the wing. Nature "hates" pressure differences, so the air above accelerates to satisfy the pressure gradient. In short, it is not that the air above and below the wing somehow "needs" to meet at the same time at the back of the wing, and since the air above needs to cover a greater distance (due to the curvature), it must travel faster – instead, the curved flow creates a pressure difference, and that pressure difference makes the air move faster above the wing, generating lift.

Figure 1: The airfoil wing (Source: DOI:10.1088/1361-6404/ac78a8)

When air flows over the wing, the thin layer of air just next to the surface (called the boundary layer) tries to follow the wing's curved shape. But if the wing is at too high an angle of attack, the airflow can no longer smoothly follow the surface. This is because, near the back of the wing, the crowded streamlines move away from one another and the pressure gradient prefers the air to slow down. On top of that, the layer of air in contact with the surface experiences further viscous drag (as compared to the air farther away from the surface of the wing). Due to the combination of all these effects, the air slows down, loses energy and eventually "breaks away" from the wing. This is called boundary layer separation. When this happens, smooth airflow turns into messy turbulence, lift drops suddenly, and the airplane can stall. Modern wings, slats and flaps are designed so that the boundary layer stays attached as long as possible, delaying separation and helping the airplane fly safely at slower speeds.

Figure 2: Boundary layer separation (Source: Aviation Stack Exchange)

The flow of a fluid is steady if at any given point, the velocity of each passing fluid particle remains constant in time. The path taken by a fluid particle under a steady flow is a streamline. Take a non-spinning ball moving relative to a fluid. The streamlines around this ball are symmetric above and below the ball, and the velocity of the fluid above and below at corresponding points is the same. Thus, there is no pressure difference. The ball moves neither up nor down. Now, take a ball in a fluid which is moving *and* spinning clockwise. This ball drags the fluid with it. The ball is moving forward and relative to it, the fluid is moving backward. The velocity of the fluid above the ball relative to it is greater than that below the ball (since the ball is spinning clockwise). The streamlines get crowded above and there is a pressure difference above and below the ball. The result is a net upward force. The airfoil shape is such that it can generate lift when it moves horizontally through a fluid (it need not spin like the ball).

Now, let us look at the various parts of a typical modern airliner.

Figure 3: The various parts of an airplane. The undercarriage or the system of wheels that support the plane on ground is known as the landing gears, which are retracted during flight. (Source: aviationfile.com)

Take-off

Take-off is one of the most crucial phases of flight. After the V_1 speed (the speed during the take-off roll after which the take-off can't be cancelled), the elevators, located at the trailing edge of the horizontal stabilizers (the smaller set of wings present at the rear end of the airplane), are moved upward to divert airflow upward. The reaction force of the air pushes down the back of the airplane. This causes the airplane's nose to tilt up during the ground run. The velocity at which this happens is known as VR or V -Rotate, since the body of the airplane rotates. After this, the plane lifts off. This is the V_2 speed. Upward and downward movements of the elevator are also responsible for changing altitude in flight.

The wings are shaped and designed to generate lift force while kept in fluids (air is a fluid). In older planes, the wings were positioned perpendicular to the body. In most modern planes however, the wings are slanted or swept backward. This design actually decreases the lift by a small amount, but increases the speed by a great extent, compensating for any decrease in lift. However, the lift generated by the main wing by itself is not sufficient to provide the energy needed to let the airplane break free of the ground.

For this reason, the wings are equipped with certain movable control surfaces – the leading-edge slats and the trailing edge flaps. Before take-off, these are extended downward – and the curvature of the airfoil wings becomes more pronounced. The low-hanging flaps also help to obstruct and slow down airflow below the main wing. Slower air is denser and is more high-pressured – and this generates extra lift. Operating the flaps is complicated, and flaps are extended to different extents depending on the weight, runway length, weather etc.. Flaps help to maximize the lift force at a particular angle of attack, without stalling the airplane and without airflow separation. (Contrary to common misconception, flaps do not change the angle of attack – rather increases lift force at a given angle of attack.) The higher the angle of attack, the higher the lift force. However, there is a limit to this. If the angle of attack is too high, as we have seen the airflow above the wing separates from the surface and creates turbulent wind vortices. This kills lift and the airplane is unable to climb further. This condition is known as a stall.

It is clear that the main wing (and the entire airplane, for that matter) is very complex. Even slight design tweaks cost millions of dollars – but these are effective as long as they increase the fuel efficiency and safety of the airplane.

THE “VR-FLAP” DESIGN

Take-off is crucial since it is impossible to slow down the airplane at such high velocities – and the length of the runway is not infinite. Larger planes can’t operate in shorter runways; heavier planes need more runway to take-off. Tailwinds and hot air also don’t help in the process. Improving take-off efficiency is, thus, always important.

From the beginnings of flight, we have devised ingenious ways of improving take-off efficiency of airplanes. Flaps are used for this reason. Increasing the surface area of the wing also helps. Modern planes also have raked wings and winglets. The wings are curved upward to increase efficiency.

The design proposed in this article has been referred to as the “VR-Flap” design. This indicates that it is an additional flap structure in the main wing that would help rotation at VR speeds during the take-off. Conventionally, this is done by the elevator. The “VR-Flap” design is basically a design tweak that could be introduced in airplanes to maximize take-off performance and pitch performance.

In this model, a downward-movable control surface is added at the leading edge under the airplane’s main wing (in the region nearest to the fuselage). The VR-Flap should be added such that it can fold right inside the wing and does not, in the slightest, modify the smooth airfoil surface of the wing. The VR-Flap essentially resembles a split flap, but set further forward. Split flaps are inefficient and increase drag. However, unlike split flaps, the VR-Flap is not meant to be activated for a long time. Thus, the resulting drag would be negligible.

Figure 4: The lateral side view of the wing is shown, with the proposed VR-Flap structure.

The design is more efficient if the airplane has a wider wing surface. For instance, in this case, the Airbus A380 would stand a greater advantage than airplanes like the Boeing 737, which has relatively thinner wings. The VR-Flap need not be too thick, but should span a huge area. During the take-off roll, on reaching VR speed, the VR-Flap can be moved down to increase the lift under the leading edge of the wing. A cautiously-engineered sudden movement of the VR-Flap could, reasonably, provide enough lift force to the aircraft so that it can break ground without activating the elevators (or it can break ground using much less runway, if the elevators are activated in addition).

While the inconvenience and cost of installing such a structure in a commercial airplane is formidable, it can come in handy in case of malfunctioning elevators, as well as helping in-flight maneuvers during rough weather conditions. However, the most important use of the VR-Flap design is of course that, if activated along with the elevators, it could reduce take-off space and/or increase maximum take-off weight of any airplane considerably. And at times, this becomes important, even if it means installing an entirely new structure in the wing.

DISCUSSION

The major concern is that such a design would considerably affect the fuel capacity as the fuel, in most planes, is stored inside the main wing. However, though costly, the fuel could be stored inside the VR-Flap too, and the joining point between the main wings and the VR-Flap could serve as the fuel pipe from the VR-Flap to the wings, and to the engines.

With the aid of the VR-Flap, in case of short runways or other emergency situations, the airplane, already at take-off roll, could easily take-off even below VR speed rather than abort the entire procedure, which at times becomes impossible. In this way, accidents like runway overruns during take-offs etc. could be avoided. It may prove effective in controlling turbulence, and with a balanced connection to the lift spoilers on the wings, the horizontal stabilizers may not need any movable surface at all. However, the horizontal stabilizers must be present anyway, for in-flight stability.

Other than the costs involved, there is no direct problem with the VR-Flap design. The question of airflow separation is also immaterial if the VR-Flap is moved down for a small instant of time. However admittedly, using both the elevator and the VR-Flap simultaneously increases the risk of tail strike (or the tail hitting the ground). Also, perhaps the most important question is the extent by which the VR-Flap needs to be moved down. In planes that sit low on the ground, this might be a problem – since the risk of the VR-Flap grazing the runway presents itself. Fortunately, modern airplanes usually have good ground clearance. Some airplanes like the Boeing 737 sit lower on the ground – but it still probably is high enough for the VR-Flap operations. Another problem with the VR-Flap design is that the jet engines in most modern airplanes are positioned in the leading edge of the main wings, which is also the proposed position for the VR- Flap. The VR-Flap could be designed in parts – and be accommodated under the wing with a gap for the engine pylons. Repositioning the engines is not always a valid option, since engines positioned at the leading edge of the main wings are more efficient and convenient than engines placed at the rear fuselage. Aft-mounted engines have some benefits, but wing-mounted engines are, on the whole, better and easier to maintain. Some older models, like the Boeing 727, had engines placed at the back of the fuselage. Setting up the VR-Flap would be more convenient in such models.

The VR-Flap design would also be very convenient to install in high-wing airplanes. Most commercial airplanes are low-wing, that is, the body is placed over the wing. Some airplanes, like some regional jets and cargo airplanes, have the main wing mounted over the body (high-wing). The center of mass is beneath the center of lift in a high-wing airplane, thus causing it to be more inherently stable as compared to a low-wing airplane (whose center of lift is below the center of mass). To improve the stability of a low-wing aircraft, designers compensate by angling the wingtips upward (dihedral). Both high-wing configurations and low-wing ones have their own benefits, and none of the designs is better than the other. For instance, in an emergency water landing, passengers of a high-wing airplane cannot use the wing, while the wing is accessible in a low-wing airplane. While high-wing airplanes have more ground clearance, low-wing airplanes have enhanced ground performance. While low-wing airplanes have the wings to reduce the impact during a crash landing, the fuselage in high-wing airplanes must take the full impact. High-wing airplanes have less space for retracting the landing gears, low-wing airplanes can do so easily in the wings.

An important point to note here is that low-wing airplanes have reduced elevator and rudder effectiveness, since the main wing blocks some of the air that flows to the rear end of the plane. This might justify installing the VR-Flap structure to aid elevators and increase the effectiveness of maneuvers.

CONCLUSION

William Boeing said, "We are embarked as pioneers upon a new science and industry in which our problems are so new and unusual that it behooves no one to dismiss any novel idea with the statement that 'It can't be done!'" In this spirit, we briefly and qualitatively explored a new design tweak that might improve take-off efficiency of airplanes.

It can be concluded that adding a downward-movable structure at the leading edge of the main wing in an airplane might help considerably in increasing take-off efficiency and the effectiveness of in-flight pitch control. It would also be very helpful in many emergency situations. Though costly, such a structure could help planes take-off below usual speeds, in short runways and in adverse conditions. Things like ground clearance, wing configurations, engine positioning etc., need to be considered before installing such a structure. However, such a structure is possible to be installed in almost any airplane. It should be most convenient to install such a structure in low-wing or high-wing airplanes with good ground clearance, and preferably with aft-mounted engines. Of course, before implementation in an actual airplane, the consequences of this added structure must be properly analyzed using numerical simulations.